

THE ROLE OF KHOREZM FOLK ART IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN CULTURE

Matkarimova Nazokat Maksudovna

MA'MUN-UNIVERSITY"

Doctor of Philosophy in History, PhD., Associate Professor

e-mail: ms.mnm.79@mail.ru

Annotation

The article discusses the art of giving, halfa and dance of the Uzbek people, its role and significance in enhancing the spiritual culture of the Uzbek people. The issue of educating Khorezm folk art in the spirit of boundless respect for one's people, the Motherland, and national traditions by instilling it in the minds of young people is also covered.

Keywords

Khorezm folk art, folklore, musical art, bakhshi, epic, epic schools, bakhshi music, song, musician, hafiz, , Art, khalfa single singing and ansamble of khalfa singers, songsand dance.

INTRODUCTION. In studying the history of the Uzbek people, an objective scientific analysis of spiritual values is of great importance, the basis of which is mainly folk art: traditional epic poetry, bakhshi, halfa, dance and other types of art. The history of traditional folk art is closely connected with the deep world of social thought, the development of which has been formed over the centuries inextricably linked with the ethnic history of the people. That is why Uzbek folk art is distinguished by its immense richness and constant freshness. Folk art is an incomparable treasure, and its instillation in the minds of young people is of great importance in educating them in the spirit of unlimited respect for their people, homeland, and national traditions.

Every nation in the world attaches great importance to the fact that its national holidays and events, family ceremonies are rich and beautiful, held in a cheerful and joyful mood. The songs, epics, folk dances and national folk games performed at such events not only illuminate the life, history, ethnography, and religious beliefs of the Uzbek people, but also embody the worldview, realities of life, dreams, and aspirations, spiritual, cultural, and material world of the people [2,98].

In the territory of Khorezm, which has long been a center of culture and art, unique folk songs, halfa halfa, maqom (suvora) samples, bakhshi and dance art occupy a wide place. At the same time, there is a need to thoroughly study the history of bakhshi halfa and dance art, conduct fundamental research in this regard, and implement many more measures to collect and publish monuments of folk oral creativity.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. In ancient and medieval times, the sacred book of the Zoroastrian religion, the Avesta [1, Avesta], ancient Turkic scripts and Sogdian inscriptions [2, Ahmedov B.A.], Alpomish [3, Alpomish], and Abu Raykhan al-Beruni's works, "Relics of the Ancient Peoples" [4, Abu Raykhan Beruni], are of great importance in the study of intangible folk oral creativity. In the Soviet period, V.M. Zhirmunsky [5, Zhirmunsky V. M., Zarifov Kh. T], H. Zarifov [6 Zarifov H.], B. A. Karriev [7, Karriev B. A], T. Mirzaev [8, Mirzaev T], M. Murodov [9, Muradov M], B. Sarimsakov [10, Sarimsakov B] and others are of great importance. Also, during the Soviet period, a number of dissertations were defended on the traditions of Uzbek folk epics and the art of bakhshi. Among these studies, one can include the dissertations of A. Kahkhorov [11, Kahkhorov A], and N. Qurbanova [12, Qurbanova N]. In the field of folk oral creativity, scientific research has been conducted in a wide range of areas in the fields of folklore, literary studies, psychology and philosophy, but bakhshi, khalfa and dance art have not been studied comprehensively from an ethnological perspective.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. Based on this, the following work can be carried out to study this topic:

Firstly, written sources on the history of traditional folk art: studying manuscripts and documents and conducting field expeditionary research.

Secondly, studying the formation and types of bakhshi art, the role of folk epics in Khorezm bakhshi art, and the issue of the transformation of bakhshi art;

Thirdly, analyzing the formation of khalfatism in Khorezm and the Khorezm khalfas, their repertoires;

Fourthly, studying the peculiarities and transformation of dance art in Khorezm;

Fifthly, showing the importance of folk art in educating young people in the spirit of unlimited respect for the homeland and national traditions.

It serves to develop the art of bakhshi, khalfa and dance, further increase the role and significance of their creativity in Uzbek culture and art, as well as create educational and methodological literature, promote them in our country and abroad through the media and the Internet, provide material and spiritual support for the activities of master bakhshis, khalfas and dancers, scientists and specialists in the field, talented young bakhshis, khalfas and dancers, and educate the younger generation in the spirit of courage, honesty, national and universal values, and high loyalty to the homeland and the heritage of ancestors.

In our country, extensive work is being carried out to preserve and protect the masterpieces of intangible cultural heritage created on the basis of the high artistic creativity of our people during the years of independence, to restore the ancient traditions of folk oral creativity and consistently

develop national values, and to promote the best examples of the creativity of bakhshis and khalfas in cooperation with creative associations. In particular, we can cite the resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 24, 2017 No. PP-2995 “On measures to further improve the system of preservation, research and promotion of ancient written sources”, dated November 1, 2018 No. PP-3990 “On holding the International Festival of Bakhshi Art”, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 7, 2010 No. VMQ No. 222 “On approval of the State Program for the protection, preservation, promotion and use of objects of intangible cultural heritage in 2010-2020”, dated April 24, 2018 No. 304 “On measures to further develop and improve the art of Bakhshi and epic poetry” and other regulatory legal acts related to this activity.

Conclusion. Musical genres used at weddings and ceremonies are still preserved in the life of our people, performed in their original form or in a revived, staged (folklore-ethnographic ensembles) interpretation, and have gained a certain importance in the process of developing socio-artistic thinking. Such efforts to restore and develop traditional dostan, bakhshi, halfa, dance and other arts and their examples, which are firmly embedded in the way of life of the Uzbek people, and at the same time to assimilate and revive them into the structure of ethnic traditions, serve as an important factor in preserving the mentality of the nation and strengthening its unique character.

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